

Supplementary material for:

Negative body size-dependent resource allocation underlies conspicuous sexual ornaments in a territorial damselfly

Results

Effect of treatment on larval development

Food provided to the medium and low food treatments was almost always completely consumed before the next feeding, however, some food provided to the high food treatment always remained by the subsequent feedings, indicating that the amount of food provided to the high food treatment was *ad lib*. Controlling for family, larval developmental time between egg hatch and emergence (high-female: 118.7 ± 1.9 days, $n = 27$, high-male: 120.7 ± 2.6 days, $n = 15$, medium-female: 126.2 ± 1.8 days, $n = 24$, medium-male: 136.7 ± 2.1 days, $n = 17$, low-female: 148.9 ± 2.2 days, $n = 12$, low male: 162.4 ± 2.3 days, $n = 16$) differed significantly among treatments ($\chi^2_1 = 153.96$, $p < 0.001$). The amount of time a larva was subjected to a treatment before emergence (high-female: 95.8 ± 1.3 days, high-male: 101.8 ± 1.4 days, medium-female: 105.8 ± 1.3 days, medium-male: 115.8 ± 1.9 days, low-female: 123.3 ± 2.0 days, low male: 135.7 ± 2.0 days) also significantly differed among treatments ($\chi^2_1 = 129.93$, $p < 0.001$). Although the difference in treatment duration partially diminished the differences among food treatments, total dry weight fed still significantly differed among treatments (high: 293.77 ± 4.24 mg, medium: 216.20 ± 5.39 mg, low: 184.02 ± 3.79 mg, $\chi^2_1 = 290.88$, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, forewing length differed significantly among treatments for both male offspring (high: 65.15 ± 0.61 mm, medium: 63.82 ± 0.63 mm, low: 63.10 ± 0.74 mm, $F_{2, 36} = 6.05$, $p =$

0.005) and female offspring (high: 61.12 ± 0.49 mm, medium: 59.12 ± 0.48 mm, low: 59.14 ± 0.52 mm, $\chi^2 = 13.09$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.001$).

Nutrition sensitivity of the white wing band

Although the male of male white wing band increased with total dry weight fed, this relationship becomes non-significant after controlling for body size (dry weight fed: $\chi^2 = 1.63$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.20$, body size: $\chi^2 = 10.19$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.001$), indication that the nutrition dependence of the male white wing band is primarily mediated through body size scaling.

Figure S1. Lack of significant relationships in male offspring between standardized residual from regressing white wing band area on body size and (a) dry fat reserve mass and (b) dry thoracic muscle mass. Grey arrow in (a) represents an outlier excluded from analysis.

Figure S2. Positive relationships in female offspring between total dry weight fed and area of (a) hind wing, (b) the white wing tip.

Figure S3. Lack of significant relationship between the brightness of the white wing tip and body size, measured as hindwing area